

Instruct-ULTRA

www.structuralbiology.eu/network/Instruct-Ultra/home

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP1 - Advancing Instruct through Instruct- Ultra

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Project objective:

To expand engagement with new communities to become part of Instruct-ERIC and bring new knowledge and capacity to the Infrastructure.

Executive summary:

The Instruct-ULTRA dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan sets out a formal communications strategy that defines the scale and direction of Instruct-ERIC's engagement activities with user groups, industry, policy-makers, funders and industry. A stakeholder analysis has been carried out to guide where the effort should be invested to achieve the most useful outcomes and an implementation plan formulated. Part of the plan will be to promote the activities of Instruct-ULTRA which underpin the communications strategy of Instruct-ERIC. Key to the communications tools are the website, videos, and representation through publications, conferences and events. Exploitation requires careful measures by Instruct-ERIC members. The plan runs for 24 months and includes regular evaluation and monitoring.

Instruct-ULTRA Dissemination, Outreach and Exploitation plan

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1. Introduction

Instruct-ULTRA aims to widen the access and scope of services available through Instruct-ERIC to the Structural Biology community, both in Europe and worldwide. In this context, dissemination is the planned process of providing information on results and outcomes from the science supported and enabled by Instruct-ERIC, to key stakeholders and the wider structural biology community at large. Outreach refers to activities designed to widen the access and participation to any populations who may benefit from Instruct activities. Exploitation will allow significant findings to be put to good use by the wider research community in further research activities, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities¹.

Information to be communicated by Instruct-ERIC includes:

- Basic information about Instruct-ERIC
- Services provided by Instruct-ERIC and how to access them.
- Scientific results from Instruct-ERIC and their users.
- Information about how to join Instruct-ERIC.
- Information about training events and workshops.
- Calls for proposals (internships, pilot R & D projects).
- Training materials about methods (online tutorials etc.).
- News of scientific discoveries in the general field using new structural biology methods.
- Involvement by Industry.
- Information and links to EU projects involving Instruct-ERIC (including Instruct-ULTRA).
- Role and deliverables of Instruct-ULTRA.

¹ <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/>

2. Stakeholder Analysis

In order to develop an appropriate communication strategy, a subgroup of the Instruct-ULTRA Executive Board was asked to score stakeholders for power and interest² which were averaged (Table 1) and plotted onto a scatter graph (Fig 1.) for analysis.

Stakeholder	Power	Interest
Instruct-ERIC / ULTRA Executive board and WP leaders	8.0	8.3
Instruct partners	6.3	7.5
Instruct research participants	5.5	8.0
Academic staff from participating RIs	5.8	6.8
Institutional senior management from participating RIs	7.5	5.3
Government research ministries (participating)	9.3	6.3
Government research ministries (not yet participating)	5.3	3.0
Academic RI User	2.5	7.3
Industrial RI User	3.8	2.8
Industry management	5.0	1.8
Industry associations / bodies	4.5	1.3
Research funders (external to governmental)	3.8	1.8
EU / ESFRI	8.8	7.8
Structural Biology community	4.5	5.3
General medical research / pharmacology communities	3.3	1.8
Structural Biology Associations and Networks	3.8	2.5
Media	4.0	0.8
Journal Publishers	5.0	1.5
Industrial Technology Developers and manufacturers	5.0	4.3
Students / Early career researchers	1.0	6.0

Table 1. Summary of Stakeholder Analysis

² Power in this case refers to a stakeholder's ability to exert influence over the project in the form of decision-making power, budgetary power, or resource power. Interest refers to a stakeholder's interest in the project results.

Fig. 1. Stakeholder Analysis Graph

We can group the stakeholders into four categories: allies, supporters, bystanders and latent, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Stakeholder Analysis Diagram

We will prioritise communications to our allies (Instruct-ULTRA Exec, Instruct-ULTRA participants, Instruct-ERIC participants, EU/ESFRI, Government research ministries, Senior management of research infrastructures and Academic research infrastructure staff). In general, we want to increase interest in all stakeholders, in the diagram above shown by the big blue arrows, moving from left to right. Choosing appropriate communication tools for each group will be important (picked up in section 5 below).

3. Extend reach of Instruct-ERIC

A key focus of the communications plan is to extend the reach of Instruct-ERIC, and the strategy needs to reflect this. There are three areas to extend into:

- Other bioscience fields. Although Instruct-ERIC is well received within the field of structural biology, other communities such as pharmacology, vaccinology, molecular biology, and general medical research could benefit immensely from structural biology techniques.
- Industry is yet to capitalise on the opportunities within Instruct-ERIC.
- New countries. Instruct-ULTRA has a role to develop Instruct-ERIC partnerships into new countries including Eastern Europe and Mercosur.

General promotion via the website and social media will be extended – posting relevant articles and attracting followers from different fields, countries and industries. Most effective, however, will be intentional personal contact between Instruct members and key individuals in these areas. Communication tools such as videos and a dissemination kit will be made available.

A set of PR resources will be produced and published to target new countries for Instruct-ERIC membership.

4. Relationship between Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA

Since Instruct-ULTRA runs alongside Instruct-ERIC, with a purpose to enhance and widen access to Instruct-ERIC, it makes sense that much of the communication and dissemination activities of ULTRA will be fed into the existing ERIC channels. ULTRA has a limited time frame, and exists to promote ERIC. Already there are mailing lists and social media accounts set up for ERIC, and since the stakeholders overlap to a large extent, our primary strategy is to make use of these channels, rather than duplicate efforts.

At the same time, we want to highlight the Instruct-ULTRA brand and its distinct purpose, allow for publication of pilot project results and development of new techniques. There is, therefore, a need to have Instruct-ULTRA specific communications, and an Instruct-ULTRA website has been established for this purpose.

The Instruct-ERIC logo reflects the brand identity of Instruct developed during the preparatory stage of the Research Infrastructure.

A project logo for Instruct-ULTRA has been created in order to assure to the project an attractive visual identity, and to foster its immediate observer recognition. The logo builds on the Instruct-ERIC logo, with a consistent colour palette. Any future printed documents or presentations can be double branded with the Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA logos side by side.

A final point relating to branding of Instruct-ULTRA is that all documents and website will display the EU logo and text about H2020 funding.

5. Communication Tools

Diverse audiences require a diverse range of communication channels. Here below we summarise the effectiveness of different tools for each stakeholder group.

<i>Level of Engagement</i>		<i>Collaborate</i>	<i>Involve</i>	<i>Consult</i>	<i>Inform</i>
Communication Tool		Allies	Supporters	Latents	Bystanders
Visual Identity		***	***	*	*
Web-based communications	Website	***	***	***	***
	Social media	*	**	*	*
	Factsheet (electronic)	**	**	*	*
	Video	*	***	**	**
	Newsletter	***	***	*	*
	Email marketing			*	*
	Third party websites	*	**	*	**
Third party newsletters	*	**	*	**	
Personal Engagement	Meeting in person	***	***	*	
	Conference presentations	**	**	**	**
	Exhibiting at events	***	**	*	
	Host events / workshops	***	***		
Print media	Brochures / PR material	*	*	*	
	Scientific publication	**	**	**	**
	Project report	*	*		
	Conference poster	**	**		*
	Press release	*	*		*

Table 2. Assessment of the efficacy of different communication tools for each stakeholder group (***) very useful, ** useful, *limited value)

6. Implementation

The different communication tools that will be used to deliver the Dissemination, outreach and exploitation plan for Instruct-ERIC are detailed below arranged in order of priority according to the assessment of efficacy (Table 2).

6.1 Websites

The original Instruct website remains the primary communication tool for the Research Infrastructure: <https://www.structuralbiology.eu/>

A major refresh and upgrade of the site is underway to improve its "look and feel". Content will be migrated to the new site by mid-2018: <https://www.instruct-eric.eu/>

Tools for analysis of site traffic and interest will be incorporated (e.g. Google analytics and Piwik). It is critical that the website content is kept updated, with fresh material regularly published to ensure repeat visits. The use of an RSS feed will be considered, perhaps in a blog format. All Instruct-ERIC will be asked to send information about news, events and job opportunities to the Instruct-ERIC hub for updating the website directly.

A separate website for Instruct-ULTRA has been set up with the following URL and will be further developed with project-specific content (e.g. deliverable reports):

<http://instruct-ultra.eu/network/Instruct-Ultra/home>

The colour palette and design will be in keeping with the current Instruct- ERIC website to show that the two projects are related, but different enough to be distinct. The Instruct-ULTRA website will be actively maintained by the Instruct-ULTRA project manager.

6.2 Video

Video is one of the most powerful ways to communicate a message. A key task within the communication project is to create a set of new videos to promote Instruct-ERIC to new audiences. The videos will be based on short interviews with participants, and focus on the benefits of Instruct-ERIC. An assessment will be made of how much work could be completed in-house before further planning and costing is made.

6.3 Publications, conferences and events

Publishing research and technical papers has a strong long-term impact on the awareness and adoption of project results. Presenting papers at scientific or industry conferences communicates results in a more impactful way, and has the benefit of stirring active discussion with attendees.

Members of Instruct-ERIC will be surveyed each year to ask about conference / meeting attendance and to liaise about how Instruct-ERIC and ULTRA will be represented. A summary list of conferences and meetings will be made available. Of particular significance is that Instruct-ULTRA will run a workshop 'Women in Science' in the 2019 at the Instruct Biennial Structural Biology Conference. This is being led by our Greek partner, The National Hellenic Research Foundation.

6.4 Dissemination Kit

Several tools have been developed to assist in personal engagement, such as a set of slides for Instruct-ERIC partners to use at the end of scientific presentations at workshops and conferences. We propose adapting the design of the slides to be more engaging and applicable to the different audiences we are trying to reach, and repackaging the materials as a "Dissemination Kit" which will be launched at the Instruct-ULTRA annual meeting in March 2018. The kit will include:

- Information sheet. A short document outlining the main features of the project.
- Slides to introduce Instruct-ERIC.
- Sign up cards for members to write down contact details and any requests from new researchers they meet at conferences who want to be added to our mailing list.
- Business cards with Instruct-ERIC branding available to any Instruct-ERIC centre platform staff who request it.
- Instruct-ERIC stickers to attach to Instruments and laboratories, visible during lab tours.
- Partners profile sheet listing the partners along with a link to their website.
- Electronic factsheet to introduce Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA

6.5 Newsletter

Instruct-ERIC has an email newsletter sent out twice a year, to a mailing list of 6100 people. Instruct-ULTRA news will be featured within this central newsletter. The December 2017 newsletter led with the announcement of Instruct-ULTRA pilot research projects.

6.6 Social Media

Twitter offers the most dynamic way of communicating project news, and increasing awareness of our project. The @Instructhub twitter account for Instruct-ERIC is well established with a good following. As of January 2018, there are 1200 followers. Posts relating to Instruct-ULTRA will be sent via the Instruct-ERIC account.

In considering ways to extend the reach of Instruct-ERIC, we propose setting up new Twitter accounts for each of the countries who partner in Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA, e.g. Instruct-FR, Instruct-NL etc. These sub accounts will initially be set up and coordinated by the Instruct Hub, and will subsequently be handed over to national partners to maintain.

Facebook and LinkedIn have not been so widely used by Instruct-ERIC. We plan to pilot the use of these channels. After review, if there is enough interest generated, to make these a focus. To monitor the effectiveness of social media campaigns, we will track activity, prominence, and follower numbers using Google Analytics and Hootsuite.

6.7 Specific Marketing to Industry

We will promote links with business schools e.g. Said Business School (Oxford, UK) and Grenoble Ecole de Management (France) to offer a 6 month internship for MBA students tackling the marketing of Instruct-ERIC to SME and larger industrial partners.

7. Time frame for communications

A time frame for implementing the communication plan is summarised in Figure 3 with three phases envisaged over 24 months (2018 -2020) for which some preparatory work has already been done.

Fig. 3. Communication plan time frame

8. Roles and responsibilities

Key to widening outreach will be to use existing partner networks. We already have good links with a number of networks, who have featured Instruct news on their websites and newsletters, for example EMBL and ESRF. A first step will be to identify and contact other partner networks.

Such networks may include:

- National structural biology networks
- Technique specific international networks
- Partnerships around academic institutes
- Technology and industry forums
- Research and industry associations

All Instruct-ERIC and Instruct-ULTRA partners will be expected to contribute to this effort according to their role, using all available tools, e.g. participating and giving presentations at conferences, publishing papers, networking, producing resources. A central point of contact for external communications will be established by the Instruct-ULTRA project manager at the Instruct Hub. However, Instruct-ERIC members should ensure that the public disclosure of information does not compromise the possibility of generating intellectual property rights from the results of Instruct-ERIC supported activity.

9. Exploitation of results

Instruct-ERIC members are expected to take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of their results from Instruct-ERIC activity by: (a) using them in further research activities; (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process; (c) creating and providing a service, or (d) using them in standardisation activities. Critical to this will be careful annotation of methods by researchers, along with open access for all publications³ and depositing digital research data⁴ for which the Instruct-ULTRA Grant agreement makes specific requirements. Effective exploitation of results from a commercial perspective depends on protecting any intellectual property (IP) via deposition of patent applications and copyrighting. However, the results must be judged to be of sufficient commercial interest or value to justify taking steps to protect them. The nature of the results will determine the most appropriate choice of IP protection as shown in Table 3.

³ As described in the Grant Agreement (GA) Article 29, relating to open access publications, beneficiaries must:

1. a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
2. b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - • on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - • within six months of publication in any other case.
3. c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication

⁴ Regarding the digital research data generated, according to GA Article 29, the beneficiaries must:

- (a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications as soon as possible;
 - (ii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the ‘data management plan’;
- (b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

Subject matter	Patent	Trade mark	Industrial design rights	Copyright	Confidential information
Invention	x				x
Software	x			x	x
Publication				x	
Design of product		x	x	x	
Name of product, project or service			x		
Know how					x
Website		x	x	x	

Table 3. Protection of intellectual property (adapted from European IPR Helpdesk Fact Sheet How to manage IP in Horizon 2020: project implementation and conclusion).

10. Evaluation of dissemination and outreach

Critical to the success of the Communication Plan is regular evaluation, monitoring and adjustment.

An outreach form will be produced as part of the Dissemination kit, which all Instruct-ERIC members can use to report back on new contacts and enquiries made at various outreach events. Include name of stakeholder / number of stakeholders, issues discussed, follow up activities, and contact details.

Metrics to be monitored include:

- Number of visitors to website
- Number of new twitter followers
- Number of new people signing up for the newsletter
- Number of conference presentations
- Number of exhibitions
- Number of publications
- Number of new technologies available at Instruct centres

The Plan will be reviewed annually, to update and adjust the planned activities based on the situation at hand.